

Synthesis of Coumarins and Chromones from Halogenated and Nitro-cresols.

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In view of the generalisation made by Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 31) that the phenols which readily yield coumarins with β -ketonic esters in presence of sulphuric acid also give coumarins and not chromones in presence of phosphorus pentoxide and the phenols which give coumarins with sulphuric acid with poor yield or do not react at all, produce good yields of chromones, and in view of the influence of the halogen and nitro group on the formation of chromones (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 25, 31), it occurred to us that the chromone condensation (Simonis' reaction) could be facilitated by the introduction of halogen and nitro groups into the molecule of those phenols which do not satisfactorily respond to the coumarin condensation (Pechmann's reaction).

The present investigation describes the condensation of chloro- and nitrocresols (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) with acetoacetic ester and α -alkyl-acetoacetic esters, both in presence of sulphuric acid and phosphorus pentoxide and the following results have been obtained:

(1) The presence of a chlorine atom in the molecule of cresol (*o*-, *m*-, and *p*-) diminishes its reactivity in Pechmann's reaction forming a coumarin and increases its reactivity in Simonis' reaction forming a chromone.

(2) The presence of a nitro group in the cresol molecule has an inhibiting influence in the coumarin condensation, but a favourable influence in chromone condensation under Simonis' conditions. Thus 4-nitro-2-methylphenol and 2-nitro-3-methylphenol do not condense with the acetoacetic esters using sulphuric acid as a condensing agent, although the chromones are easily obtained using phosphorus pentoxide.

(3) The presence of an α -substituent in the acetoacetic ester molecule produces a hindrance in Pechmann's reaction, which increases with the complexity of the substituent but it has no marked influence in the chromone condensation in Simonis' reaction.

(4) The 2-methyl-group in chromones is always reactive irrespective of the position and nature of the substituents in the benzene ring (*cf.* Heilbron, Barnes and Morton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, Cheema, Gulati and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 925). The chromones, described in this paper, have been characterised by the formation of styryl derivatives by condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide as the condensing agent. The formation of a styryl derivative serves to distinguish a 2-methylchromone from the isomeric 4-methylcoumarin.

(5) The results are in full agreement with the generalisation made by Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*). If there is no formation of a coumarin or if the formation of a coumarin is slow in Pechmann's reaction, then the chromone formation is generally facilitated in Simonis' reaction.

It should be noted that Simonis' reaction is invariably attended with the formation of a considerable amount of resinous product and the isolation of the product in the purest form is always a matter of difficulty and the yield of the product in the case of the chloro- and nitro-cresols never exceeds 10-15% of the theoretical.

The coumarins and chromones, derived from 4-chloro-3-methylphenol, may have the alternative structures (I) or (II) (R = Me, Et, Pr,

(I)

(II)

etc.) and it has not been possible to distinguish between these two structures on account of the low yields of the products.

Robertson, Waters and Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1681) detected the formation of pairs of isomeric 1:4-pyrones when Simonis' reaction was applied to *m*-cresol and methyl- and ethyl-acetoacetic esters, but in the case of chloro-*m*-cresol, however, only one product has been isolated and it has been described as (I).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The chloro-cresols *e.g.*, 4-chloro-2-methylphenol, 2-chloro-4-methylphenol, 4-chloro-3-methylphenol, have been prepared by the action of sulphuryl chloride on the cresols (Peratoner and Condorelli, *Gazzetta*, 1898, 28, i, 197; Mezzarn and Lamberti-Zanardi, *ibid.*, 1896, 26, ii, 399).

2-Nitro-3-methylphenol has been prepared according to the method of Hodgson and Beard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 498). While preparing 2-nitro-3-methylphenol following the method of Gibson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1272) a yellow substance melting at 94° was obtained. On analysing it was found to be a dinitro compound, probably identical with the 2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (m.p. 99°) described by Nietzki and Ruppert (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3479).

To a cold solution of *m*-cresol (21.6 c.c.) in fuming sulphuric acid (6.7% sulphur trioxide, 80 c.c.) a mixture of fuming nitric acid (9.3 c.c.) and fuming sulphuric acid (6.7% sulphur trioxide, 21.3 c.c.) was slowly added with mechanical stirring, the solution being cooled in a freezing mixture. Water (100 c.c.) was added and superheated steam at 145-150° was passed. A yellow oil came over with the steam which ultimately solidified. It was filtered, m.p. 94°. (Found: N, 13.7. $C_7H_6O_5N_2$ requires N, 14.1 per cent).

Preparation of the Coumarins.—The cresol (1 mol.) and the acetoacetic ester (1 mol.) were treated with 1½ times their weight of H_2SO_4 sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) and the mixture kept overnight. The solution was then poured into powdered ice, when the product separated either as a solid or a thick oil, which on washing with caustic alkali solution yielded a solid. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid or alcohol (charcoal).

Preparation of the Chromones.—A mixture of the cresol (5 g.) and the acetoacetic ester (5 g.) was heated with phosphorus pentoxide (10 g.) on the water-bath for 1 hour. More phosphorus pentoxide (10 g.) was then added and the mixture further heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. On adding powdered ice to the reaction mixture a thick oil was generally obtained, which was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with 2*N*-caustic alkali and then with water, dried over calcium chloride and the ether removed, when crystals were obtained. The adhering oily impurity was removed on the porous plate and the product was crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid (charcoal).

Preparation of the Styryl Derivatives.—The chromone (0.2 g.-0.3 g.) was dissolved in the least quantity of absolute alcohol and the solution was treated with benzaldehyde (0.5 g.) and an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (0.5 g. of sodium in 5 c.c. of absolute alcohol). After keeping overnight the solution was heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, when crystals separated from the boiling solution or on cooling or on adding a few drops of water. The crystals were collected, washed with dilute alcohol and finally crystallised from alcohol or acetic acid.

The chlorine in these compounds has been conveniently estimated by the semi-micro method (ter Meulen, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1928, **47**, 698) and the nitrogen in some of the compounds has also been estimated by the semi-micro method (ter Meulen, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1934, **53**, 121).

The coumarins and chromones derived from 4-chloro-2-methylphenol, 2-chloro-4-methylphenol, 4-chloro-3-methylphenol and the acetoacetic esters are described in Table I.

The chromones derived from 4-nitro-2-methylphenol, 2-nitro-3-methylphenol and the acetoacetic esters are described in Table II.

TABLE I.
Coumarins and Chromones from Chloroacets.

Name.	Formula	Prepared from	Condensing agent.	M. p.	Solvent from which crystallised.	Analysis.
6-Chloro-2 : 8-dimethylchromone	$C_{11}H_9O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-2-methylphenol and acetoacetic ester.	P_2O_5	130°	Dilute acetic acid	Found : Theo : 17.1% 17.6%
The styryl derivative	$C_{16}H_{13}O_2Cl$	—	—	176-78°	Alcohol	12.05 11.9
6-Chloro-2 : 3 : 8-trimethylchromone	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-2-methylphenol and methyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	113°	Acetic acid	15.7 15.9
The styryl derivative	$C_{16}H_{15}O_2Cl$	—	—	164°	Alcohol	11.3 11.4
6-Chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-4-ethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-2-methylphenol and ethyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	128°	Acetic acid	15.1 15.0
The styryl derivative	$C_{18}H_{17}O_2Cl$	—	—	154°	Alcohol	10.7 10.9
6-Chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-3-propylchromone	$C_{14}H_{15}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-2-methylphenol and propyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	120°	Acetic acid	16.6 14.1
The styryl derivative	$C_{18}H_{19}O_2Cl$	—	—	135°	Alcohol	20.3 20.4
8-Chloro-4 : 6-dimethylcoumarin	$C_{11}H_9O_2Cl$	2-Chloro-4-methylphenol and acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	105°	Acetic acid	17.5 : 17.04
8-Chloro-3 : 4 : 6-trimethylcoumarin	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$	2-Chloro-4-methylphenol and methyl-acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	152°	Acetic acid	16.0 15.9

TABLE I (contd.).

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from.	Condensing agent.	M. p.	Solvent for crystallisation.	Analysis Found: Theo:
3-Chloro-2 : 3 : 6-trimethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2Cl$	2-Chloro-4-methylphenol and methyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	150°	Acetic acid	Cl, 16.0% Cl, 15.9%
The styryl derivative	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2Cl$	—	—	183°	Alcohol	11.54 11.4
3-Chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-3-ethylcoumarin	$C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$	2-Chloro-4-methylphenol and ethyl-acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	146°	Acetic acid	14.8 15.0
3-Chloro-2 : 6-dimethyl-3-ethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$	"	P_2O_5	105°	Acetic acid	14.7 15.0
The styryl derivative	$C_{13}H_{17}O_2Cl$	—	—	132°	Alcohol	10.7 10.9
3 : 8-Dichloro-4 : 6-dimethylcoumarin	$C_{11}H_9O_2Cl_2$	2-Chloro-4-methylphenol and α -chloro-acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	110°	Alcohol	28.8 29.1
6-Chloro-4 : 7-dimethylcoumarin	$C_{11}H_9O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	208°	Acetic acid	17.5 17.03
6-Chloro-3 : 4 : 7-trimethylcoumarin	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and methyl-acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	146°	Acetic acid	16.6 15.9
6-Chloro-2 : 3 : 7-trimethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and methyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	94°	Acetic acid	15.9 15.9
The styryl derivative	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2Cl$	—	—	153°	Alcohol	11.6 11.4
6-Chloro-3-ethyl-4 : 7-dimethylcoumarin	$C_{11}H_{11}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and ethyl-acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	136°	Acetic acid	14.8 15.0

TABLE I (contd.).

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from.	Condensing agent.	M. P.	Solvent for crystallisation.	Analysis Found:
6-Chloro-3-ethyl-2:7-dimethyl-chromone	$C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and ethyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	113°	Acetic acid	Cl, 15.1% N, 15.0%
The styryl derivative	$C_{20}H_{17}O_2Cl$	—	—	155°	Alcohol	11.0 10.9
6-Chloro-3-propyl-2:7-dimethyl-chromone	$C_{14}H_{15}O_2Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and propyl-acetoacetic ester.	P_2O_5	92°	Acetic acid	14.0 14.1
The styryl derivative	$C_{20}H_{17}O_2Cl$	—	—	—	Alcohol	10.5 10.4
6-Chloro-7-methyl-coumarin-4-acetic acid	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and acetone dicarboxylic acid	H_2SO_4	185-88°	Acetic acid	13.6 14.05
3:6-Dichloro-4:7-dimethylcoumarin	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2Cl_2$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and α -chloro-acetoacetic ester	H_2SO_4	210°	Acetic acid	29.5 29.1
6-Chloro-4:7-dimethyl-coumarin-3-acetic ester	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4Cl$	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol and ethyl aceto-succinate	H_2SO_4	110-12°	Acetic acid	12.08 12.1

TABLE II.

Chromones from Nitroresols.

6-Nitro-2:3:8-trimethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{11}O_4N$	4-Nitro-2-methylphenol and methyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	245°	Acetic acid	N, 5.8% N, 6.0%
The styryl derivative	$C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$	—	—	225°	Alcohol	4.2 4.3
6-Nitro-2:8-dimethyl-3-ethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$	4-Nitro-2-methylphenol and ethyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	233°	Acetic acid	5.9 5.6
The styryl derivative	$C_{18}H_{17}O_4N$	—	—	205°	Alcohol	3.9 4.1

TABLE II (contd.).

Chromones from Nitrocresols.

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from.	Condensing agent.	M. p. crystallisation.	Solvent for Analysis	Found : Theo :
6-Nitro-2 : 8-dimethyl-3-propyl-chromone	$C_{14}H_{15}O_4N$	4-Nitro-2-methylphenol and propyl-acetoacetic ester.	P_2O_5	200°	Acetic acid	N, 5.27% N, 5.30%
8-Nitro-2 : 7-dimethyl-3-chromone	$C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$	2-Nitro-3-methylphenol and acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	136°	Alcohol	6.2 6.30
8-Nitro-2 : 7-dimethyl-3-ethylchromone	$C_{13}H_{15}O_4N$	2-Nitro-3-methylphenol and ethyl-acetoacetic ester	P_2O_5	137°	Alcohol	5.1 5.66

The authors' thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for giving them facilities to carry on this investigation.

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Received September 3, 1936.